

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D2.4

Report on Communication Materials

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History of changes

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
DCP	Dissemination and communication plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
RO	Research Object
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform

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1 Executive Summary

This document introduces the RELIANCE project communication materials used during the first year of the project activities. These materials are the result of the dissemination and communication plan (D2.3) which has been delivered at M3 of the project.

During the first year, the main objective of dissemination and communication activities within the RELIANCE project has been three-fold:

1. To ensure the promotion of RELIANCE services and the overall project, with the scientific communities (e.g., RELIANCE services users) involved in the project as early adopters.
2. To support RELIANCE dialogue and coordination on communication activities with the other Infra-EOSC7 projects and support EOSC Future project activities
3. To support the RELIANCE Open Call activities to extend the usage and adoption of its services to non-Earth Science communities.

The list of materials, events and project collaborations will be constantly updated and adjusted as the project dives into its second year of activities. A second release of the current document is foreseen at M24.

2 Introduction

Dissemination and promotional activities are fundamental actions to ensure the adoption of RELIANCE project services. These activities are expected to be carried out among a spectrum of initiatives to keep updated and inspire the entire community, which involves Stakeholders, Scientific Researchers and Institutions. This document lists items, materials, videos, and Social Media channels that are used to ensure a valuable source of information on the principal characteristics of the project and its demonstrators.

2.1 *Covid limitations to Media Productions*

Due to the coronavirus pandemic, all meetings, presentations at national or European congresses have been carried out online. Consequently, no physical means of communication – e.g., rollups, brochures, flyers – were implemented during the first year or are planned to be implemented during the second year.

The focus of dissemination activities – and therefore the present and future major investment – was to optimize online communication mainly through info animations and video pills showing how RELIANCE services can be used by the scientific communities. Video pills and tutorials are currently planned to be published through the main media used for communication between the early adopters of the RELIANCE services and external stakeholders as they have proven to be very effective in facilitating early adopters' understanding of how RELIANCE Services learning work.

2.2 Strategy for Wp2 Communication activities

The main advantage of adopting the RELIANCE services is their complete availability and onboarding in the EOSC Hub environment. The experience gained during the EVER-EST project – RELIANCE predecessor – showed how vital demonstrating the impact of the services on every day scientists' activity is. The learning curve to understand the RELIANCE core technology - based on Research Objects and the two integrated additional services providing Text Mining and data cube capabilities - is steep: stakeholders will confront with an overwhelming set of information, including innovative services and technologies that can be difficult to digest all at once.

The idea behind such services, the possibility to use them for cross-disciplinary research and the portfolio of added-value services that can be derived must be supported by practical demos carried out by RELIANCE scientific partners that will allow early adopters outside the consortium to fully assess their value and innovative potential.

Nonetheless, two dimensions must be taken into account to fully understand the approach taken to create dissemination materials during the first year:

1. RELIANCE services are under refinement and their first major release is planned across the end of Year 1
2. RELIANCE is a very technical initiative: the budget is allocated for activities development and services testing by the communities, and around 3% is allocated for pure communication and dissemination activities

The considerations above have led the consortium to dedicate the first year at assembling and preparing communication and dissemination material; at preparing RELIANCE project communities for training activities and video pills realization; at interoperating and creating a dialogue with InfraEOSC Projects and the EOSC Future project and initiatives.

In parallel – as detailed in project reports – a huge effort has been spent to create a set of clusters of non-Earth Science players whose might be interested in joining the Open Call planned for M14.

The core social and massive communication with external communities will be concentrated during the last 8 months of the project: this aims to optimize budget allocation on T2.2 and perform a focused communication campaign based on services that are available, integrated, well known and used by the different communities.

3 Communication Materials

3.1 RELIANCE Logo and document templates

In RELIANCE, the logo is shown as a graphic item and the title of the be used for all communication and dissemination activities. A simplified iconic version is also provided for official documents and presentation templates.

Figure 1 RELIANCE Logo and Lettering

Figure 2 RELIANCE Logo and Lettering – B/W

Figure 3 RELIANCE Logo (200x200)

On every RELIANCE document templates, information of EU funding is present by means of a prominently displayed EU emblem and the Grant Agreement: “This project has received funding from the European research infrastructures (including e- Infrastructures) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017501”.

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Title

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Figure 4 RELIANCE Deliverable and documents Template

Figure 5 RELIANCE Power Point template – Intro

Figure 6 RELIANCE Power Point template – Chapter

Figure 7 RELIANCE Power Point template – blank

3.2 RELIANCE Website

The RELIANCE website www.reliance-project.eu - is the main entrance for the project and the most important source of information on activities within the project. It is structured into three main sections:

- Landing page – providing full information about the entire project, its' communities, services and its role within the EOSC Hub Environment.
- Services page – providing details on each single service, including description, added value for researchers, examples
- Scenarios page – providing details on each user communities scientific scenarios. Services are tested and validated in this section.

In addition, a News and Update page – providing all the latest information about the project – and the connect page to be used for further information and that will represent the starting point for external

communities of early adopters to check in and get in contact with service providers and RELIANCE user communities.

	<p>INTRODUCTION</p> <p>VIDEO PILLS</p> <p>VISION</p> <p>STATISTICS RO's and users</p> <p>INTRO TO SERVICES</p> <p>SERVICES AND EOSC</p> <p>COMMUNITIES</p> <p>NEWS and UPDATES</p> <p>OPPORTUNITIES ENGAGEMENT</p> <p>CONSORTIUM</p> <p>Get In touch</p>
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Figure 8 RELIANCE Website Landing Page

SCIENTIFIC SCENARIOS
Services Portfolio for Research Lifecycle Management

RELIANCE services will be validated by research scenarios and grand challenges involving three scientific consortiums: Sea Monitoring, Atmospheric Monitoring and Geo-Research. Each consortium will provide RELIANCE with domain specific use cases. At the same time the consortium will work to maximize interaction and cross-fertilization across disciplines.

Research scenarios and grand challenges

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RELIANCE GRAND CHALLENGES

- Sea pollution**
To understand and quantify the impact of marine litter and to reduce its presence in the ocean. This multidisciplinary scenario investigates the role of physical and biological processes in the marine pollution setting and accumulation of plastics in the marine environment, from their sources to the sea.
- Loss of Biodiversity and Sustainability**
Global warming and ocean acidification are predicted to engage on deep sea ecosystems with deleterious consequences on their biodiversity. This multidisciplinary scenario targets the consequences over Mediterranean and coral habitats quantifying under realistic conditions very close to 1.4°C.
- Extreme weather events and climate adaptation**
This use case is going to combine satellite data and in-situ observations with climate model outputs and geospatial data analysis tools to assess the extent of the Arctic warming effect, while also engaging with local populations and climate managers with a view to better manage their pasture and vegetation.
- Reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions**
Reducing the consequences of large volcanic eruptions. Eruptions release tremendous amounts of ash about the average height of four systems units high with a major disruptive event. We will focus in particular on health and air dispersion and follow from real-time volcanic eruptions, SO2 clouds dispersal, and their interactions with the atmospheric and marine environments.

Multidisciplinarity

The opportunity comes from the unique wealth of data retrieved during lockdown in 2020 were the anthropogenic impact on our environment less pronounced. We will:

- USE THE LOCKDOWN CONSEQUENCES**
An opportunity to assess the impact of air quality and air dispersion and to reduce the consequences of large volcanic eruptions.
- EXTEND THE COOPERATION**
Extend the cooperation between the different scientific communities.

THE CHALLENGE

To test the evolution
The challenge is to test the evolution of the pollution related to the marine environment and to reduce the consequences of large volcanic eruptions.

To quantify in a synoptic way
The challenge is to quantify in a synoptic way the pollution related to the marine environment and to reduce the consequences of large volcanic eruptions.

To integrate measures
The challenge is to integrate measures to reduce the consequences of large volcanic eruptions.

NEWS & UPDATES

- RELIANCE PRESENTED @EAS-ACE public launch event**
The Reliance project was presented at the EAS-ACE public launch event on 12 and 13 December 2020. The event was held in a hybrid format, combining a physical event in the Reliance project office and a virtual event for the wider community.
- Open Science is all about cooperation and Re-Use!**
Open Science is all about cooperation and Re-Use! The Reliance project is committed to open science and to the reuse of data and information.
- RELIANCE Project has been kicked off!**
The Reliance project has been kicked off! The project is now officially underway and we are looking forward to the many achievements to come.

Reliance

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Reliance is supported by the European Union

SERVICES
In a service of scientific research management

Reliance offers a suite of proprietary and interoperated services designed to facilitate the management of Earth Science Communities and European Users.

What you can do using RELIANCE suite of services ?

The overall goal of the Reliance project is to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic approach, not just at the level of the data, methods, code or publications individually, but of the whole research lifecycle as a first-class citizen.

Based on 3 complementary technologies

Reliance proposes a research lifecycle management service ecosystem based on three complementary and interoperated technologies:

ROHub

ROHub is a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management and preservation of scientific observations, campaigns and geospatial processes via research objects.

It makes these resources available to others, allows to publish and release them through a DOI, and allows to discover and reuse pre-existing scientific knowledge. Built around the research object concept and inspired by sustainable software engineering practices, ROHub is the reference platform implementing the full research object model and paradigm, which provides the backbone to a wealth of EO-centric applications and interfaces across different scientific communities. ROHub comprises a backbone service, exposing a set of RESTful APIs, a reference Web client application (see picture below), and integrates multiple end-user research object services (e.g. discovery, usability, enrichment, etc.).

<https://rohub.ecmwf.eu/>

RELIANCE, ROHub will be interconnected with the other RELIANCE services, namely ADAM platform for Data Cubes services and text mining and semantic enrichment services. ROHub will be interconnected with the EOSC portal catalogues, and will leverage and integrate with other EOSC services, including EOSC AAI and research data management services like BIODID, BIODIVE or Zenodo.

Advanced geospatial Data Management

The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform (ADAM) is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data.

ADAM allows the extraction of global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and long term projections. Most of the data is updated daily to allow users to always have the most recent data to play with. Besides in Web GUI allowing users to explore, access, visualize and download data (see picture below), it offers an API enabling access to the data access and processing capabilities directly from the user's code and applications.

<https://adamm.ecmwf.eu/>

RELIANCE, ADAM will be interconnected with ROHub, e.g., enabling a single sign-on between the services, as well as enabling researchers to open a data-cube-centric research object in the ADAM interface, or to open back data cubes in a research object. It also plans to leverage and reuse existing EOSC services, including EOSC AAI, storage services (e.g. BIODID/BIODIVE), computing power to manipulate heavy data cubes, and the Hadoop services for processing them.

Text mining

Text mining and analytics services help user communities to tap into the information encoded in text that is produced across all the stages in the scientific endeavor.

These services transform raw descriptions coming from research resources into structured data. The structured data extracted from research resources is semantic metadata that describe the content of the text beyond the traditional keywords and text snippets, including named entities, multiword expressions, and concepts. Semantic metadata is a key enabler of the FAIR principles since it helps to increase the reliability of the research resource, thus fostering their sharing and reuse. In addition, semantic metadata can be used to deliver more accurate search results and content-based recommendations.

Open Collaboration Software partners feature – <https://ecmwf.eu/technology/2020/08/20/2020-08-20-ecmwf-ai/> and full analytics services that can support the scientific enterprise.

RELIANCE, text mining services will be interconnected with ROHub, e.g., enabling a single sign-on between the services, to automatically search the stored research objects and to facilitate the reuse of the output of the analytics services in support of the scientific enterprise (e.g., influential networks, analytics dashboard, etc.).

Integration with EOSC components

Reliance

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Reliance is supported by the European Union

Figure 9 RELIANCE Web pages for Challenges & Communities (left) and Proposed Services (right)

3.3 Social Media

Social media channels used by RELIANCE include Twitter and LinkedIn. The Twitter account is mainly used to keep connections with all EOSC and INFRA EOSC related stakeholders, initiatives and projects.

Figure 10 RELIANCE Twitter account

The LinkedIn account is currently used at internal level by project partners and will be used to extend the services users base to additional cluster in connection with the Open Call specifications.

Figure 11 RELIANCE LinkedIn account

3.4 RELIANCE Info Animations

The RELIANCE partners involved in WP2 have proposed and realized an animated video in order to reach out to a wider audience and allow familiarizing with the main elements of the project initiative. The purpose of the video is to trigger interest in the project and invite more people to visit the website that will be connected to the open call due at M14. The video animation was executed by PSNC under the coordination of Terradue and Alpha with a major contribution from the RELIANCE scientific partners. It is currently available at the main page of the project landing page as a quick summary of the initiatives, and published on Twitter and LinkedIn.

Figure 12 First RELIANCE video animation

The first video¹ identifies the needs of Open Science communities to share research findings through virtual research environments. The need to tackle a multi-disciplinary approach, to share resources and jointly work on cross-disciplinary scenarios. The Venice Lagoon example shown in the video is a real use case scenario developed during the project.

Figure 13 Second RELIANCE video animation

The second video² focuses on the RELIANCE services offer, introducing their objectives and how they can be used by the scientific communities for research purposes.

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1H-y14ln2w>

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w39xvNrqTR8>

Figure 14 Third RELIANCE video animation

The third video animation³ is dedicated to the Open Call for Early Adopters, explaining the initiative and how new scientific communities can join the consortium for multi-disciplinary – even non Earth Science – scenarios development.

3.5 Video Pills

In the preparation of future dissemination and communication activities – during pandemics – we believe that engaging the scientific communities in the presentation of the services and how they can help researchers in their everyday activities represents a crucial aspect.

- Scientific communities will get used to communicating in a brief and efficient way the services, a key aspect for their RELIANCE ambassadorship when tackling a new community of early adopters
- Video Pills are a very efficient and modern media to disseminate the services offer in an easy way, creating a link with new users that can therefore express their interest by getting involved in meetings to discuss specific details.
- Having the scientific communities at ease with generating video pills will allow creating the training materials in a faster and more efficient way.

The first two video pills are planned to be delivered at the end of M13. The storyboards, the images and the live interviews have been recorded: infographics to support the videos are currently under production as well as all the post-production activities required to create a professional result.

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=36QuVTGJSds>

Figure 15 Preview of CNR video on Research Objects

Figure 16 Preview of INGV video on Research Objects and Data Cubes

4 Conferences and Meetings

4.1 Attended Conferences

Events are profoundly relevant in disseminating information about RELIANCE, and engaging different stakeholders and potential early adopters. With the addition of EOSC Hub and INFRAEOSC7 related events. The list below includes events attended by RELIANCE representatives during the first year. The list is organized by Presenters. Conferences and meetings do not include the work carried out in the frame of EOSC Future which is an ongoing process, with infra-projects meeting scheduled monthly since July 2021.

Date	Venue/ Project	Project	Presenter
18.1.2021	Invited seminar at the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VUA), Netherlands	Title of the talk: Building a Principled Partnership with Thoughtful AI in Science	Jose Manuel Gomez Perez
5.2.2021	EGI/ ACE: Public launch event	RELIANE Project	Raul Palma
2.3.2021	Invited Seminar at University College London, UK	Title of the talk: On the Role of Knowledge Graphs and Language Models in Machine Understanding of Scientific Documents	Jose Manuel Gomez Perez
3.3.2021	On line/ GEANT	Introduction to RELIANCE	Raul Palma
10.3.2021	On line/ OpenAire-Nexus: Public launch event	Introduction to RELIANCE	Raul Palma
11.3.2021	On line/ RO-crate: EOSC community call	Introduction to RELIANE	Raul Palma
18.3.2021	OpenAire-Nexus:	Bilateral (OpenAire-Nexus – RELIANCE) projects synergies identification	Raul Palma Oscar Corcho Jose Manuel Gomez Perez Esteban Garcia Daniel Garijo Malgorzata Wolniewicz
28.05.2021	Greco Webinar	Extending the research-enabling capabilities of EOSC	Raul Palma
18.3.2021	Advisory Board: Bilateral information exchange with Sheila JJ Heymans, Executive Director European Marine Board	Bilateral information exchange	Federica Foglini Raul Palma

15.3.2021	GÉANT	Synergies teleconference with Chris Atherton Senior Research Engagement Officer	Raul Palma Pedro Goncalvez Simone Mantovani
1.7.2021	Invited seminar at University of Trier, Germany	Title of the talk: Towards AI that Understands Science and Beyond	Jose Manuel Gomez Perez
6.10.2021	AISTAR - Artificial Intelligence Symposium on Theory, Application and Research	Title of the talk: Pick your Poison - Data Hunger vs. The Knowledge Bottleneck in Language Understanding	Jose Manuel Gomez Perez
24.5.2021	MetOS group (meteorology and oceanography)	RELIANCE project	Anne Foilloux
7.7.2021	Galaxy Community Conference 2021	RELIANCE project	Anne Foilloux
11.8.2021	UIO	2 summer internships meeting to start using Jupyter notebooks and ROHub	Anne Foilloux
24.9.2021	MetOS (Meteorology and Oceanography) and Njord (Centre for Studies of the Physics of the Earth)	Update on RELIANCE services	Anne Foilloux
5.10.2021	Pangeo Europe	Introduction of ADAM data cube	Anne Foilloux
13.10.2021	Sigma2 (the Norwegian e-infrastructure for research and education)	Introduction to the RELIANCE project and ROHub service	Anne Foilloux
14.10.2021	EOSC-Future Review	Demo with EGI notebook, ADAM-API and ROHUB services	Anne Foilloux, Federica Foglini
15.10.2021	MetOS internal call	RELIANCE services for Climate Science	Anne Foilloux, Federica Foglini
1-8.11.2021	FORCeS eScience course	Introduction of the RELIANCE project Introduction to ADAM platform and ADAM-API	Anne Foilloux

23.11.2021	The Alan Turing Institute (UK)	Adoption of ROHub for the Environmental Data Science Book	Anne Foilloux
08.10.2021	TCS-ICS federated system for the EPOS Delivery Framework	Presentation of RELIANE services, discussion on the metadata formats to be adopted.	Elisa Trasatti
28.10.2021	Soprintendenza Beni Culturali - Naples	Meeting to introduce the Research Object concept, and the possible applications for their archive. Preparatory meeting to their possible interest on the Open Calls.	Elisa Trasatti
3.11.2021	EPOS Joint Research Unit Italy	Presentation of the RELIANCE services for possible interest of EPOS in implementing the RO paradigm.	Elisa Trasatti
16.12.2021	INGV Data Management Team	Presentation of ROHUB to discuss possible connection with the INGV Data Portal.	Elisa Trasatti
13/14.01.2021	ITEM (innovation of the improvement of the marine ecosystem)	Presentation of RELIANCE	Federica Foglini
25/26.02.2021	Meeting on Marine Geology	Presentation of RELIANCE	Federica Foglini
30.03.2021	CNR ISMAR meeting	Presentation of RELIANCE and RO Hub	Federica Foglini

4.2 Publications

Currently one publication has been delivered by project partners

Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate

Article type: Research Article

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5 Conclusions

This document has provided evidence of the materials used during the first year of the project. It is clear that within a pandemic situation, presenting the project services and results in face-to-face events will be difficult, and therefore no printed material is foreseen for the second year of the project, as it was during year 1. In addition, it is critical to creating the dissemination, training and communication tools that will be used once the services are delivered in their final version to maximize their adoption and usage by the scientific communities. This will include mainly video pills creation in form of presentations and tutorials.